

Effect of Acetone and Ethyl Alcohol on Briggs-Rauscher Oscillating Reaction

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IN connection with the investigation on hydrogen peroxide-iodic acid-Mn²⁺-acetoacetic ester oscillating system (Briggs-Rauscher reaction¹) it appeared interesting to examine the effect of acetone² (which itself is also an organic substrate for this reaction) and ethyl alcohol on the oscillation parameters. Attempts have been made to explain the experimental results in the light of the mechanism known so far.

Experimental

The reaction was studied in phosphoric acid³ medium in the absence and presence of acetone or ethyl alcohol in different concentrations. The reaction was started by the addition of potassium iodate-phosphoric acid mixture to the reaction vessel containing acetone (or ethyl alcohol), hydrogen peroxide and starch-manganous sulphate-acetoacetic ester mixture, which were taken earlier in the said order. The concentrations of the components in media are shown in Tables 1 and 2. No reactant was further added during the reaction and the systems were expected to behave as closed in the thermodynamic sense. The reaction mixture was stirred by a magnetic stirrer at a more or less fixed rate. The oscillations were followed by striking

(and beautiful) colour changes from colourless to golden to pink (or blue). The oscillation parameters like induction period, oscillation period, total number and total time of oscillation, time of appearance of white turbidity and time of appearance of permanent blue colour or precipitate indicating cessation of oscillation were noted. The experimental results have been summarised in Tables 1 and 2 and the plots of oscillation period against time at different concentrations of acetone or ethyl alcohol are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

The following interesting observations have been made :

- (i) An increasing concentration of acetone (or ethyl alcohol) causes a decreasing trend in the total number and total time of oscillation.
- (ii) The oscillation periods decrease with increasing concentration of acetone or ethyl alcohol.
- (iii) The time of appearance of permanent blue colour or precipitate decreases with increase in the concentration of acetone or ethyl alcohol.
- (iv) The presence of acetone or ethyl alcohol appears to hasten the appearance of white turbidity.

Most of these observations may be qualitatively explained in the light of the mechanism proposed by Cooke and others⁴⁻⁸. For oscillatory behaviour, Briggs-Rauscher system is believed to involve

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ACETONE

[EAA]=0.035 M, [H₂O₂]=0.928 M, [IO₃⁻]=0.053 M, [H₂PO₄]=0.079 M, [Mn²⁺]=0.005 M and [Starch]=0.016%

Set No.	Acetone% (v/v)	Induction period (time of appearance of first pink colour) Sec.	First 3 oscillation periods Sec.	Average of first 3 oscillation periods Sec.	Total no. of distinct oscillations	Total time of distinct oscillations (including induction period) Sec.	Time of appearance of permanent blue colour or precipitate Sec.
I	nil	28	13, 19, 19	13	~36	384	not sharp
II	5.26	not sharp	9, 8, 8	8	~37	339	—do—
III	10.52	—do—	5, 6, 6	6	~32	236	—do—
IV	15.78	—do—	4, 5, 5	5	~23	161	228
V	21.04	—do—	3, 4, 3	3	~8	76	190

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ETHYL ALCOHOL

[EAA]=0.03 M, [H₂O₂]=0.818 M, [IO₃⁻]=0.046 M, [H₂PO₄]=0.068 M, [Mn²⁺]=0.005 M and [Starch]=0.014%

Set No.	Ethyl alcohol% (v/v)	Induction period (time of appearance of first pink colour) Sec.	First 3 oscillation periods Sec.	Average of first 3 oscillation periods Sec.	Total no. of distinct oscillations	Total time of distinct oscillations (including induction period) Sec.	Time of appearance of permanent blue colour Sec.
I	nil	32	18, 16, 15	16	26	~312	670
II	6.82	—	12, 13, 8	11	13	~159	510
III	13.64	25	9, 9, 7	8	21	~165	375
IV	20.46	22	6, 6, 5	6	19	~119	246
V	27.20	not sharp	2, 3, 4	3	8	~106	197

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NOTES

Fig. 1. Effect of acetone on B-R reaction using ethylacetoacetate.

Fig. 2. Effect of ethyl alcohol on B-R reaction using ethylacetoacetate.

switching between two limiting steady states of high and low iodide ion concentrations. Iodine is produced by a radical process when the iodide ion concentration is low and consumed at high iodide ion concentration. Iodine production involves the iodine dioxide oxidation of manganese(II) with subsequent rapid reduction by H_2O_2 and the gross reaction is represented by

Iodine is consumed by the organic substrate like acetoacetic ester giving iodo-derivatives.

Iodous acid is believed to play a role similar to that of bromous acid in Belousov-Zhabotinskii reaction. For radical production leading to iodine we have the principal fate of iodous acid as (1)

and for high iodide ion concentration (the conditions prevailing during iodine consumption) the principal fate of iodous acid is (2)

Switching is anticipated to occur whenever the iodide ion concentration passes through the value

$$[I^-] = \frac{k_1}{k_2} [IO_2^-]$$

For $[I^-]$ less than this value, production of iodine will dominate leading to an autocatalytic rise in iodous acid concentration limited by the second order disproportionation of this species ($2HIO_2 \rightarrow HIO_3 + HIO$). For $[I^-]$ greater than this value, iodine consumption dominates and the iodous acid concentration is maintained low.

In the present studies, as both acetone and ethyl alcohol are iodine consumers, it can be reasonably expected that the oscillation period will more and more decrease when concentration of acetone or ethyl alcohol is increased because of an increase in iodine consumption rate. Again, H_2O_2 and KIO_3 are consumed more in each cycle and hence the number of possible oscillations as also the total time of oscillation will decrease as acetone (or ethyl alcohol) concentration is increased. The permanent blue colour also appears in a shorter time as the whole process is hastened. Further studies are obviously necessary for quantitative elucidation.

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A Recalculation of pK_1 and pK_2 of *o*-Phthalic Acid at a Number of Temperatures

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PRASAD¹ has shown that Davies equation² does not correctly represent the activity coefficient γ_1 of an ion but equation (1), which he called modified Davies equation, does.

$$\log \gamma_1 = -\frac{Az_1^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + \beta_1 \mu \quad (1)$$

In equation (1) he assumed that, (i) β_1 is additive, and (ii) β_1 is reasonably independent of the composition of ionic atmosphere in dilute solutions, provided its composition is not drastically changed.

The pK_1 and pK_2 values of *o*-phthalic acid in aqueous solution from 273.15 to 333.15 K in steps of 5 K as determined by Hamer, Pinching and Acree³ and Hamer and Acree⁴, respectively, from cells without liquid junction are taken to be the most accurate values. In the present work we have recalculated pK_1 and pK_2 of *o*-phthalic acid using the data of Hamer and coworkers and the modified Davies equation to show that the assumptions underlying this equation are reasonably correct. The use of this equation considerably simplifies the calculation and gives pK_1 and pK_2 values of comparable accuracy.

By using four series of solutions having varying values of $m_1 : m_2 : m_3$ in cell (C-1) over $\mu = 0.002$ to 0.45 mol kg^{-1} , Hamer and Acree determined pK_2 .
 (Pd)H₂ | KHPH, K₂Ph, KCl, AgCl | Ag (C-1)
 | m₁ m₂ m₃

The e.m.f. of cell (C-1) and the ionic strength of cell solutions are given by equations (2) and (3), respectively.

$$E = E^0 - k \log m_H \cdot m_{Cl} - k \log \gamma_H \cdot \gamma_{Cl} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where, } k = \frac{2.3026 RT}{F} \text{ and } E^0 = E_{Ag^+/Ag, Cl^-, Cl^-}$$

$$\mu = m_1 + 3m_2 + m_3 + 2m_H \quad (3)$$

Use of modified Davies equation (1) in equation (2) gives equation (4), which in turn gives m_H by an iterative procedure, since the values of A , E^0 and k are known from literature⁶⁻⁸ and Hamer and Acree⁵ found that E^0 of cells (C-2) and (C-3) are identical over 273.15 to 333.15 K.

The values of β obtained⁹ with cell (C-2) can be used in equation (4), if the assumptions of modified Davies equation be correct.